

THE SIMULATION OF HIGH RATE IMPACT TESTS ON COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH MIXED FINITE ELEMENT TYPE ANALYSIS

W. Kong^{1,2}, R. Brooks², S. Li² and E. Sitnikova²

¹AVIC Commercial Aircraft Engine CO.LTD, 3998 South Lianhua RD,
Minhang District, Shanghai, 201108, China

²Polymer Composite Research Group,
Department of Mechanical, Material and Manufacturing Engineering,
University of Nottingham, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, United Kindom
Email: emxwk@nottingham.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.nottingham.ac.uk>

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ABSTRACT

To reduce the cost of modelling large composite structures under impact loading, a mixed finite element type analysis, involving solid elements, thin shell elements and their coupling has been developed. Simulation has been carried out in LS-DYNA for projectile impact on plain weave composite plates and a large composite aero engine casing ring. Compared to the models with solid elements only, this method provided similar prediction in terms of projectile trajectory, target deformation and material failure. When a quarter of the casing ring was model with solid elements and three quarters with shell elements, this method required only 50% of the computational resources and time used in the all-solid-element approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites are making significant inroads into the aero-engine industry due to their high strength-to-weight ratio. Substantial weight savings could be achieved in the fan components of the engine when they are made from composites instead of conventional metallic materials. This is particularly the case for the largest part of the aero engine - the fan containment casing. As required by aero administration authorities, the fan casing must be proven to be capable of containing all the high energy debris during a fan blade out (FBO) event [1]. The FBO tests are expensive and so it is vital to have reliable predictive numerical methods to guide the design and the tests for the fan casing. The transient, non-linear impacts at high velocities, during the initial stages of FBO, require explicit finite element methods [2, 3] for reliable analysis. It has been reported [4,5] that very fine meshing should be used in the impact region when modelling such events to accurately predict the damage observed in experiments. For composite materials, mesh sensitivity of the impact analyses is particularly important [6,7]. As an example, the fan of GENx has a diameter more than 2800mm [8] and thus requires a significantly large number of elements and nodes to model its fan containment casing during an FBO event.

During the FBO event, the trajectory and impact of the blade is surprisingly repeatable, despite the fact that the event occurs randomly [9]. As a result, the impact performance of a fan casing can be assessed using ballistic tests, where a projectile is fired at high velocity onto a target at an oblique impact [9]. Unlike the FBO event at engine level, which usually involves several revolutions of the rotor, the circumferential motion of the projectile in ballistic tests can be controlled, making it a well-defined localized event. This also makes it possible to perform a numerical analysis with mixed element types, in which a critical local domain modelled with three-dimensional solid elements is embedded in a global domain modelled with elements of reduced dimensions, e.g. shell elements, and the different types of elements are coupled [10]. The concept has been practiced in the marine [11], automotive and aviation industries [12], and its use has been demonstrated in the multi-scale modelling of composites [13, 14].

The purpose of this study is to understand the capability and limitations of a mixed element type analysis (META) in simulating the impact performance of composite structures. META models and all-solid-element models have been developed to simulate ballistic impact tests on composite plates [15] and aero engine casing structures [16]. The models have been solved using the explicit finite element software package LS-DYNA_971. Assessment of the META approach was made by considering impactor velocity history simulation, material damage predictions and computational efficiency measures.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Panel impact model

The investigation into the capability of META in a panel impact scenario is based on the simulation and experiments by Gama et al. [15], where air gun apparatus was used to fire cylindrical projectiles of 13.8g mass, 12.7mm in diameter and 14.02 mm in height onto plain-weave S-2 glass/SC15 composite plates. The rectangular plates had nominal thickness of 13.2mm, in-plane dimensions 178mm × 178mm and comprised 22 plies of the above composite. They were bolted between two square steel plates, both of which had a central circular hole of diameter 101.6mm. The impact velocity and residual velocity of the projectile was measured and recorded in the experiments [15].

In this study, the two steel plates were not modelled explicitly and only the material exposed from the hole was modelled. In spite of symmetric material properties and loads, a whole circular plate model was built to avoid complexity arising from element deletion at the symmetry boundaries. The no-slip boundary condition at the steel plate/composite interface was modelled by constraining the displacement of the peripheral nodes in all the directions. A single surface contact algorithm was used at all the material interfaces.

The META model for the plates (see Figure 1) has three parts i.e. the projectile, the solid region and the shell region of the composite plates. Both the solid region and the projectile were modelled using hexahedral solid elements with a single integration point. Belytschko-Tsay shell elements were used for the shell region. Multiple integration points were set up in the thickness direction to represent the layup. The meshes of the plates were varied to achieve convergence but generally they followed a similar mesh pattern, comprising a central square region (40mm × 40mm) of uniform fine mesh modelled with the solid elements, and a surrounding region meshed with the shell elements. The mesh size in the impactor was chosen to be comparable to that at the center of the plate. The mesh was carefully made so that all shell element nodes at the shell-solid interface were in alignment with the corresponding solid element nodes. Then the solid element nodes were constrained to the shell element nodes by using `CONSTRAINED_SHELL_TO_SOLID` [17]. In the current version of LS-DYNA (R7.1.2), the shell-to-solid constraint allows to couple one shell node with a maximum of 9 solid nodes, i.e. 8 elements. All-solid models have also been constructed and exactly the same mesh size as the META models.

`MAT_LAMINATED_COMPOSITE_FABRIC_58` material model [17] was used for the shell region, while `MAT_COMPOSITE_DMG_MSC_162` [17] was the material model for the solid region. Two different material models were used because appropriate identical composite material models are not available for both solid and shell elements in LS-Dyna. However, the input parameters for MAT58 were taken as a subset of the MAT162 parameters provided in [15], as listed in Table 1. It should be pointed out that the material properties are automatically scaled in MAT162 to account for strain rate dependency, but only the quasi-static properties were used in MAT58 as the strain rate effects in the shell region are expected to be small. The projectile was modelled as a rigid body with the properties of steel ($\rho=7850$ kg/m³, $E=210$ GPa, $\nu=0.29$). It was assigned an initial velocity of either 360 m/s or 800 m/s, corresponding to non-penetration and full penetration scenarios respectively, as it was reported in the experiments [15]. Energy time history was checked for each simulation to ensure the total energy of the system was constant and the hourglass energy and sliding energy were controlled to be less than 5% of the total energy.

Figure 1. The META model for the panel ballistic tests.

ρ [kg/m ³]	E1 [GPa]	E2 [GPa]	E3 [GPa]	ν 21	ν 31	ν 32
1850	27.5	27.5	11.8	0.11	0.18	0.18
G12 [GPa]	G23 [GPa]	G31 [GPa]	S1T [MPa]	S1C [MPa]	S2T [MPa]	S2C [MPa]
2.90	2.14	2.14	604	291	604	291
S3T [MPa]	SFC [MPa]	SFS [MPa]	S12 [MPa]	S23 [MPa]	S31 [MPa]	SFFC
58	850	300	75	58	58	0.3
ϕ [deg]	eLIMIX	SDelam	ω max	eCrush	eExpn	Crate1
10	0.2	1.2	0.999	0.001	4.5	0.03
m1	m2	m3	m4	Crate2	Crate3	Crate4
2	2	0.5	0.2	0	0.03	0.03

Table 1. MAT162 input properties & parameters for the plain-weave S-2 glass SC15 composite from [15].

2.2 Casing impact model

In addition to the flat panel model, a FE model of a cylinder representing a fan containment casing has been constructed. This model is mainly used here to assess the ability of the META model to save computational costs when modelling large scale components. Only limited effort was made in studying the damage and deformation of the cylindrical component, due to there being a lack of experimental results to compare with. The setup of the META models for the fan casing followed the experiment described by Roberts et al.[16] for testing composite fan case components, as shown schematically in Figure 2. Geometric simplification was made by modelling the fan case as a ring of 2000mm inner diameter, 750mm width and 20mm thickness. Furthermore, the curved fan-blade-like projectile was simplified as a long thin plate. The bottom of the ring was fixed on a support of 30° slope. The 7.8 kg projectile was fired obliquely along the horizontal direction at 120m/s to the ring, giving an energy level of 57 kJ, which is close to the value determined in [9]. META models and all-solid models were built to simulate the test. The approach for plates described in the previous section was adopted for the casing models, including the shell-solid region coupling, the material models for the composite and the contact algorithm. The projectile was also modelled with the material properties of steel. In the META model, a quarter of the casing was modelled with 5 mm cube blocks of solid elements while the remainder was modelled with shell elements. The mesh density and topology of the quarter of the casing in the all-solid model was exactly the same as the META model. The blade was

modelled with 3 layers of solid elements of uniform dimension, $2\text{mm} \times 2\text{mm}$ in-plane and 1.6 mm thickness.

Figure 2. (a) Test configuration for composite fan case impact testing. (b) The META model with quarter of the casing ring modelled with thin shell elements.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mesh sensitivity study

The plates in [15] were modelled by dividing the 22-ply composite into 12 material layers. Each of these material layers was meshed through thickness so that a layer of 0.56mm-thick solid elements was sandwiched between two layers of 0.28mm solid elements as shown in Figure 3(a). This gave 36 layers of elements through the thickness of the plate in total. The elements under the projectile had in-plane dimensions $0.56\text{ mm} \times 0.56\text{ mm}$. An identical 36 layer meshing was constructed in this work. In addition, two models with uniform element thicknesses of 0.56 mm and 0.28 mm have been considered. These resulted in a 24-layer system and a 48-layer system and they are shown in Figure 3 (b) and (c), respectively.

Finally, an even coarser mesh was considered, where the plate was divided into the material layers and had 8 elements through the thickness. A mesh sensitivity study was carried out with all-solid element models to investigate whether it is feasible to model the 22-ply composite plates with 8 layers of elements. The choice for the number of through thickness elements in this case is based on the consideration that the current shell-to-solid constraint is only able to couple 8 solid elements to 1 shell element

An initial impactor velocity of 360 m/s was used. Figure 4 shows the results for the different mesh densities in the form of predicted impactor velocity histories. The result from [15] is also given for comparison. A general trend is that the predicted residual velocities are significantly higher than that reported in [15], and there is a plate perforation even at lower impact velocity. Even for the 36-layer model, which, as mentioned, has an identical mesh density to [15], the residual velocity is overestimated. It was mentioned in [15] that an interfacial definition was used between material layers but further information is not available. However, when two element thicknesses are combined in one model, as in the 36-layer model, the velocity results are closer to those in [15]. Such mixed element thicknesses could be related to the interfacial definition. When the element thickness was varied from 0.28 mm in the 48-layer model to approximately 1.7 mm in the 8-layer model, the velocity prediction was nearly the same.

Figure 3 The through thickness mesh of one of the 12 material layers in the plate impact model, (a) The 36-layer model from [15] with a combination of elements of 0.56mm and 0.28mm in thickness; (b) 48-layer model comprising elements 0.28mm thick and (c) 24-layer model with uniform mesh of 0.56mm. The in-plane elements size in the impact region is 0.56×0.56 mm in all the three cases.

Figure 4. The predicted velocity histories for the mesh sensitivity study.

Therefore, the higher impact resistance and non-perforation failure at 360m/s reported in [15] are likely to be caused by the energy dissipation in the interfaces. However, due to lack of information regarding the interfacial definition, it was difficult to replicate these results. In order to achieve a better agreement with the experimental data in [15], trials were made by varying CRATE1, the parameter used for incorporating the strain rate dependency of material strengths. In [15], the strain rate coefficients (as given in Table 1) were obtained by fitting the predicted velocity history to the impact test data. Using this method in the present study, it was found when CRATE1 was increased from original 0.03 to 0.3, the velocity prediction at 360 m/s initial velocity agreed well with [15] as can be seen in Fig. 4. However, this was not the case at higher impactor velocities of 800 m/s, where the increased CRATE1 over-scaled the strengths and consequently over-predicted the penetration resistance of the plates. Since the value of CRATE1 was not actually determined from material tests, it was therefore used as a fitting parameter at each initial impactor velocity.

Finally, the in-plane mesh size was also varied for a convergence check. The in-plane dimensions of the elements under the projectile were increased from 0.56×0.56 mm to 1×1 mm, but this was found to make only a very small difference to the velocity history (Figure 4). Thus, based on the above discussion, the 8-layer model with in-plane element size $1\text{mm} \times 1\text{mm}$ will subsequently be used in the following plate impact study.

3.2 Plate impact model

The simulation results for the plate impact model, including impactor velocity, impactor displacement and contact force, are shown in Figure 5(a), 5(b) and 5(c), respectively. As can be seen, at an impactor velocity of 800 m/s, the predictions by the META model are nearly the same as its all-

solid element counterpart. When the impactor velocity is reduced to 360m/s, there are discrepancies between predictions for the all-solid element model and the META model. In particular, with the META model, the impactor is slowed down more quickly than with the solid model, as can be seen in Figure 5(a). A discrepancy as large as 80 m/s occurs at the early stage of the analysis, but this disappears and velocities agree well later on in the simulation (less than 10 m/s discrepancy). In Figure 5(b), the two displacement curves divert to a peak difference of 6 mm at the later stages of the simulation. In Figure 5(c), contact forces are very similar except that the secondary peak for the META model occurs 50 μ s earlier than the all-solid element model.

Figure 5. Simulation results: (a) Impactor velocity history (b) Impactor displacement history and (c) Contact force history.

The plate displacement time histories at several nodal locations are shown in Figure 6. In the META model, three nodes directly under the impactor, three nodes at the shell-solid interface and one node in the shell region are the selected locations. To give a direct comparison, the same locations are selected for the all solid-element model.

Figure 6. (a) the locations for the displacement comparison; (b) to (h) are the displacements of node 1 to 7 in (a) respectively.

Directly under the impactor, the all-solid element model moves 3mm more in the impact direction than the META model when the impactor initial velocity is 360 m/s. When the initial velocity is 800 m/s, the elements fail and are deleted very early in the simulation hence no displacement variation is recorded in some figures. At the shell-solid interface, similar displacements are predicted in the META and the all-solid model except at the bottom of the plate (opposite side to the impact), where the all-solid element model deflects 0.5 mm more at 360 m/s and 1 mm more at 800m/s. In the shell region, the difference between the META and the solid model is no more than 0.2 mm at both initial

velocities. In general, the META model predicts the deflection more accurately when the velocity is 800 m/s. The prediction by the META model has a very small discrepancy from the all-solid element model at the interface and in the shell region. Within the solid region, the META model predicts less deflection, indicating a stiffer response.

The contour plots showing three different failure modes, namely, fibre failure, in-plane matrix failure and delamination, are presented in Figure 7. The contour scale is from zero to one, which corresponds to intact and completely damaged/failed elements, respectively. These figures show a view from the bottom of the plate where the most material damage occurs. Generally, the impact at 360m/s causes larger areas of failure than at 800m/s. At 360m/s (Figure 7(a) and 7(b)), matrix failure and delamination happen in such a global manner that the failed area extends beyond the square region in the centre of the plate. In MAT58, the material model for the shell region, failure and damage is calculated but it cannot be contour-plotted as in MAT162, the material model for the solid element region. Consequently, the shell region seems intact in the META model. However, this is an artifact of the damage visualization for MAT58 and damage does extend beyond the interface into the shell region. Also at 360 m/s, fibre failure is more localised and it can be seen that the predictions for this failure mode by the META and all-solid element model agree reasonably well. At 800 m/s, all the failure modes tend to be more localised. This could be the effect of strain rate dependency, which makes the constituents stronger, especially the matrix. It could also be due to the deformation mechanism changing from large deflection at low velocity to direct punch-through at high velocity. In the all-solid element model, material failure is contained in the central square region for all the failure modes, and failure predicted by the META model is very similar to that for the all-solid element model. Only slight unrealistic failure along the interface can be observed which is likely to be due to stress concentration at the element coupling.

3.3 Casing impact model

The fan casing impact models were run on the high performance computing (HPC) system, Minerva, at the University of Nottingham. 16 cores and 64G RAM were used. The time histories of projectile kinetic energy and displacement are shown in Figure 8. The kinetic energy reached a constant value close to 0 J at 3 ms, at which point the simulation was terminated. It can be seen that very good agreement between the META model and the all-solid element model is achieved for both projectile kinetic energy and displacement throughout the simulation. There is only a 5% difference in displacement at the end of the simulation.

The contour plots of deformation and failure in the casing at 3ms are shown in Figure 9-11. In general, the indentation and the deformation of the casing predicted by the META model are very close to the all-solid element model. In both Figure 9(a) and 9(b), the casing in the region adjacent to the area of impact undergoes a rotation. In the META model (Figure 9(a)) the top left quarter of the casing was modelled as a solid-element region and the rotation is observed near the interface between element regions. In particular, at the left interface, larger rotation is predicted by the META model than the all-solid element model (Figure 9(b)). Far away from the impact region, neither deformation nor rotation is observed. The material rotation is likely to introduce a three dimensional stress state, which cannot be modelled by the shell elements. Hence an over-prediction of the rotation is made by the META model. Accuracy could be improved if the solid region is made sufficiently large such that little rotation occurs in the shell regions.

The contour plots in Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the fibre failure and fibre crush damage predicted by MAT162. Similar to the panel models, the fibre crush is a very localised failure mode, mostly concentrated in the impact region and its vicinity. The prediction for this failure mode by the META model is in very good agreement with the solid model. By contrast, fibre failure appears to be more of a global mechanism as predicted by the all-solid element model in Figure 11(a). And this failure mode extends far beyond the impact region. Again, due to the lack of implementation of a failure contour in MAT58 for shell region, fibre failure cannot be illustrated here. Nonetheless, the failure patterns within the solid region are very similar for both the all-solid element and the META models.

Figure 7. Failure modes within the plates : fibre failure (first row), matrix failure (second row) and delamination (third row), (a) Solid model at 360m/s; (b) META model at 360m/s; (c) Solid model at 800m/s; (d) META model at 800m/s.

Figure 8. The projectile displacement and kinetic energy history in the casing impact model.

Figure 9. The deformation of the casing at 3 ms in (a) the META model; (b) the solid model.

Figure 10. The fibre crush failure contour of (a) the solid model and (b) the META model.

Figure 11. The fibre failure contour of (a) the solid model and (b) the META model.

The computational savings of the above META model have been calculated by comparison with the all-solid element model, as shown in Figure 12. By modelling three quarters of the casing with shell elements, the numbers of elements and nodes are nearly halved. The running time for the same event duration is also halved. The saving in memory usage (30%) is less due to the solid-shell coupling.

Figure 12. A comparison of computing resources required for running the casing META model all-solid models.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the impact loading of composite plates and large cylinders, e.g. a fan containment casing, were modelled by mixed element type (META) finite element analyses, involving solid and thin shell elements. A mesh sensitivity study on the impact of composite plates revealed that convergence could be achieved by 8 layers through the thickness of solid elements with in-plane dimensions $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$. To replicate published experimental and simulation [15] results at relatively low impact velocities (360 m/s), the strain rate scaling factors for material strengths in the material models (LS-DYNA MAT162) were increased to compensate for impact energy dissipated by interfacial layers. Subsequently, the META models were assessed by comparing them to corresponding all-solid element models. The results show that this approach is capable of predicting accurately the projectile trajectory in flat composite plates. For the localized failure mode near the impact centre, the extent and pattern of failure predicted by the META models resembles the all-solid element models. However, the globalized failure modes can develop into the shell regions of the META models, resulting in an artificial increase in plate stiffness. This can cause the discrepancy in the target deformation and contact force predictions made by the two models. For the ballistic impact test simulations of the large composite casing rings, the META model was created, where solid elements were used for a quarter of the ring and three quarters of the ring were meshed with the shell elements. It gives predictions similar to the all-solid elements model with respect to projectile trajectory, casing deformation and material failure. This was achieved at a 50% reduction in computational resources and time.

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